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THE IMPACT OF THE ISRAEL-IRAN CONFLICT ON CENTRAL ASIAN ECONOMIES: ENERGY, TRADE AND GEOPOLITICAL REALIGNMENTS.

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the potential economic consequences of an escalation between Iran and Israel for global economic situation and for the Central Asian region. First, the study outlines the historical and geopolitical background of Iran's regional role and the origins of the Iran-Israel rivalry. It then analyses the strategic importance of regional transport routes such as those connected to the Strait of Hormuz and Iranian transit corridors.

The article contributes to the broader discussion to geopolitical situation and economic development in Central Asia, highlights the importance of diversification of trade routes in the region, also economic resilience in the face of external geopolitical shocks.

Geopolitical tensions in the Middle East have consequences that extend far beyond the region itself. Policymakers and scholars consider that escalation in one of the most significant locations, especially in the Strait of Hormuz, continues to raise potentially negative consequences for global security, international trade routes and energy markets. The modern global economy is characterized by a high level of interdependence of countries that political instability in one region can rapidly affect economic conditions elsewhere. For Central Asian countries, these changes are particularly important. The region located a strategic position between Europe, the Middle East and East Asia. Interactions between Central Asia and Iran have been shaped by deep cultural, economic and political ties. These historical connections have continued to influence contemporary relations.

Understanding the economic consequences of tensions between Israel and Iran requires explaining Iran's historical development, geopolitical position and its relations with neighboring regions. Iran is one of the oldest continuous civilisations in the world. The foundations of Iranian statehood were established during the Achaemenid Empire in the sixth century BCE, which also controlled territories stretching from the Mediterranean Sea to Central Asia in its peak times.[1]. This early political and cultural connection created long-

lasting relations between Iran and the regions of Central Asia through trade, migration and cultural exchange.

Iran's geographic position served as a bridge between several major civilizations, the Middle East, South Asia and Central Asia. At that time trade routes crossed Iran and were part of the Silk Road network for the movement of goods, people and ideas across Eurasia. In the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, Iran experienced strong political and economic pressure from external powers, particularly the Russian and British Empires. An important political turning point occurred during the Constitutional Revolution of 1905-1911, when reformers established parliament and attempted to introduce constitutional governance. During the 1960s and 1970s the Shah implemented "White Revolution" modernization policies that included land reforms, industrial development and expansion of education. However, these reforms also created social inequality and political repression which increased public dissatisfaction in Iran.[2]

These tensions led to the fall of the monarchy and established the Islamic Republic under Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini because of Iranian Revolution of 1979. The new government introduced a political system combining republican institutions with religious authority and adopted a foreign policy strongly critical of Western influence in the region.[3] This shift significantly affected Iran's relations with Israel and the United States and since then has become one of the main sources of long-term political confrontation in the Middle East.

In the modern period, Iran's geopolitical importance is also closely related to its geographic location. The country has borders with several key regions, such as the Middle East, South Asia, the South Caucasus and Central Asia. It also has access to the Persian Gulf and the Strait of Hormuz, one of the most important maritime chokepoints in the global energy system. Approximately 20-21% of the world's petroleum liquids consumption passes through the Strait of Hormuz, making it one of the most critical routes for global energy trade.[4] Any big change in this corridor can significantly affect international oil prices and global energy security.

Iran also possesses large energy resources. According to global energy statistics, the country holds approximately 208 billion barrels of proven oil reserves, which represents about 12% of global reserves and ranks third in the world, after Venezuela and Saudi Arabia.[5] Iran's role is even bigger in the natural gas sector. Iran possesses about 1,200 trillion cubic feet of proven natural gas reserves, making for about 17% of global reserves that ranks second in the world ranking after Russia.[6] Despite these large reserves, Iran's full production potential has been limited by international sanctions, as a result Iran exports less than other major producers with similar resource bases.

Additionally, Iran enlarged its regional importance through alliances and support for various political and armed groups, despite its economic impact. Iran supported in political and military aids to organizations such as Hezbollah in Lebanon and Hamas in Gaza. Israel considers that as a major security threat.[7] Iran's support for such groups viewed by Israel as a direct threat to its national security and has contributed significantly to the deepening hostility between them.

Learning tensions between Iran and Israel helps us to explain why these historical and geopolitical factors can have wider economic effects beyond the Middle East. The following section discusses the key economic aspects of such geopolitical tensions. They may affect global economies, particularly through energy markets, trade routes and financial stability with recent data in the region.

Tension in the Middle East have continued to escalate as Israil and Iran engage in a series of retaliatory strikes. Over the weekend, the conflict intensified when the United states launched airstrikes on Iranian soil, reportedly aimed at dismantling sites involving in nuclear weapon development. At present, there are no visible signs of ceasefire discussions, and the situation remains volatile, with no clear indication how far the conflict may escalate.

A key concern has emerged from Iran’s threat to close the Strait of Hormuz, through which approximately 20% of the world’s liquefied natural gas and 20-34% portion of oil trade pass. A closure of this strategic waterway would severely disrupt access to the Persian Gulf, impacting trade flows for countries like Qatar, the United Arab Emirates and Saudia Arabia and could lead to a sharp rise in fuel prices globally. [8]

This escalation creates unstable environment in middle east in which most cargo ships are avoiding routes which are crossed in middle east. The Red Sea, Suez Canal, Bab al-Mandab Strait have been disrupted by Iran backed Houthi forces. Freight suppliers returning to the Cape of Good Hope, adding approximately 3,000-3,500 nautical miles and 10 to 14 days to typical transit times through Cape town, South Africa, in order to reach their destination.[9] This makes additional charges range from 2000-4000 USA dollars for each container on freight shipment.

Infographic showing the share of crude oil transported through the Strait of Hormuz in the 1Q of 2025, by destination. (Graphic by Nicholas SHEARMAN / AFP via Getty Images) AFP via Getty Images

As we can see, the large portion of petroleum products were sold to the four giant manufacturing powers of Asia. Countries like China and India buy large amounts of oil and export many consumer goods through these straits, so they face a serious problem with goods stuck at sea. David Gonzalez, VP analyst at Gartner’s supply chain practice, doesn’t expect oil and natural gas prices to skyrocket, saying, Iran generates around 4 percent of global oil production and 6 percent of natural gas, not insignificant by any means, but not large enough to substantially move the needle on price. Yes, we saw some movement in the price of oil, but

that was to be expected following the tumultuous events of the past couple of days. [10] The conflict with Iran has removed roughly 20 million barrels per day of crude from global markets and sent oil prices to above \$80 as of press time.[11]

Public sentiment across Central Asia reflects limited support for Iran. [A May 11 to June 10, 2025 telephone survey](#) showed that most regional respondents opposed giving military aid to Iran.

In Tajikistan, 13% supported military involvement, while Kazakhstan recorded the lowest support level at 5%. Kyrgyzstan displayed the highest indecision rate, with 25% of respondents uncertain. Regarding political backing, Kazakhstan and Tajikistan exhibited higher levels of sympathy towards Iran, with 42.6% and 42.1% respectively supporting political alignment. Conversely, in Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan, opposition to political support stood at 55% and 39%, respectively.[12]

Eran serves as a transit state for the southern corridor linking Central Asia railways and port networks to Türkiye, Europe and the Gulf state. Central Asian states see Iranian ports as a gateway to the Persian Gulf and Indian Ocean notably Bandar Abbas port, which is a way to diversify export routes beyond mother corridor which link Central Asia to Moscow. Even though, there are several problems such as assess cost, risk and political uncertainty in the region, these alternative routes remain important for Central Asian states. As for how the war affects the economic situation of Central Asian countries, the impact remains to be seen. Turkmenistan, whose capital city is only 25km away from the Iranian border, is most exposed, as the country depends on Iranian imports, most critically for food and household items. Uzbekistan is less, but still somewhat exposed, as Iran is a top supplier of dairy and oil. Conversely, for the remaining Central Asian economies, losing the Iranian market is not a massive blow to imports or exports, but further direct and indirect ripple effects may be on the horizon. [13] Overall rising energy prices may also have follow-on economic effects, potentially leading to increasing budget expenditures and overall inflation.

Although Central Asian governments emphasize neutrality and de-escalation, prolonged conflict could overtax the region's ability to handle potential migration and volatile energy prices. Because the public resists military involvement in Iran, governments have domestic backing to remain neutral..

References:

- 1.Touraj Daryae, The Oxford Handbook of Iranian History (Oxford University Press, 2012).
- 2.Nikki R. Keddie, Modern Iran: Roots and Results of Revolution (Yale University Press, 2006).
- 3.Misagh Parsa, Social Origins of the Iranian Revolution (Rutgers University Press, 1989).
- 4.U.S. Energy Information Administration analysis based on Vortexa tanker tracking data
- 5.Oil Reserves by Country (2025)
- 6.Natural Gas Reserves by Country
- 7.Council on Foreign Relations, "Iran's Role in the Middle East," 2024.
- 8.Project 44: Escalating risks: The ripple effect of the Iran conflict on supply chains | project44
- 9.www.Forbes.com: Escalating risks: The ripple effect of the Iran conflict on supply chains | project44
- 10.Institute for supply management ISM: The Impacts of the Iran Attack on Supply Chains and Global Business

-
11. Thomson Reuters: The US-Iran War: The potential economic impact and how businesses can react - Thomson Reuters Institute
 12. Israel-Iran Conflict: Central Asia's Reactions and Concerns
 13. War arrives at Central Asia's doorstep | commonspace.eu

